

The Effectiveness Of Project Read, Enjoy, And Discover (R.E.A.D): Basis For An Enhance Reading Program

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Abstract

Observations within the academic setting revealed a significant concern regarding the low reading performance of graduates from Taguntungan Elementary School and Sta. Margarita West Elementary School as they transition to Grade 7. Feedback from neighboring secondary schools, namely Baggao National Agricultural School and Sta. Margarita National High School, indicated that many learners experience difficulties in reading comprehension, fluency, and overall literacy skills, which adversely affect their academic performance. These concerns prompted the researcher to implement Project Read, Enjoy, and Discover (Project R.E.A.D.), an enhanced reading intervention program aimed at improving learners' oral reading abilities and literacy skills.

The study focused on learners' difficulties in word recognition, reading fluency, and comprehension. Participants often struggled to understand reading passages, read with limited expression, and demonstrated slow reading pace with frequent pauses on unfamiliar words. The enhanced Project R.E.A.D. program incorporated guided reading sessions, vocabulary enrichment activities, oral reading exercises, storytelling, peer-assisted learning, remedial instruction, and continuous reading assessment. It also encouraged collaboration among teachers, parents, and stakeholders in promoting a supportive reading environment.

The study involved 75 Grades 4–6 pupils from the two participating schools in Baggao North District during School Year 2025–2026. Participants identified as frustration-level readers through the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) pretest that were included in the study. A quasi-experimental two-group pretest-posttest design was utilized. Data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, paired sample t-test, independent t-test, Pearson's r, and Chi-square.

Findings revealed significant improvement in oral reading performance, with mean scores increasing from 40.54 to 55.06. The computed t-value of -4.872 and p-value of .000 indicated a significant difference between pretest and posttest scores. Results confirmed that the enhanced Project R.E.A.D. program effectively improved learners' oral reading skills, fluency, comprehension, and vocabulary development.

In view of the results, the researcher proposed the continuous implementation and enhancement of Project R.E.A.D. as a sustainable school-based reading intervention program. The proposed enhanced reading program includes regular monitoring and assessment, differentiated reading activities, parental involvement, teacher capacity-building initiatives, and collaborative literacy programs aimed at ensuring continuous literacy development among learners and promoting a strong culture of reading within the school community.

Keywords: *Project READ, Phil-IRI, Reading Comprehension, Reading Intervention, Literacy Skills, BoSY, EoSY.*

Introduction

Reading is one of the most essential skills that children should learn and acquire in order to understand everything around them, to explore what is beyond, develop their own skills, and cope up with their studies. It is the most important skill to master to ensure success in learning that will make them competitive individuals for their future careers as asserted by Smith, J. et al. (2017).

The World Bank and UNESCO developed the concept of learning poverty as a way to measure children's progress in basic reading and comprehension skills. In a 2022 report, the World Bank stated that the Philippines' rate of learning poverty stood at 91%, meaning that number of ten-year-old pupils were unable to read and understand age-appropriate texts.

These are serious problems that need intensive reading programs in schools and must focus on the importance of letter recognition and phonetic awareness as supported by research from the National Reading Panel (2000) and Adams, M. (2015) for them to read little by little. They cannot able to read if they cannot recognize letter sounds and can blend these sounds to pronounce a word. These crucial stages of early childhood development must be guided by the parents, teachers, and also, some knowledgeable others that could offer their time and effort in teaching the child on how to read.

There are many problems that beginning readers encounter in school as identified by the researcher, Snow, C. et al., (2019) most especially when they are not yet ready and not yet equipped for the reading stage. Some encounter difficulties in letter recognition, phonetic awareness, sound blending, word recognition, and reading comprehension.

With these problems, the researcher aimed to strengthen reading skills to address the issue through a reading intervention program. This reading intervention program is called the "Project R.E.A.D" which means "Read, Enjoy, And Discover".

Observations within the academic setting revealed a significant concern regarding the low reading performance of graduates from the two participating schools—Taguntungan Elementary School and Sta. Margarita West Elementary School—as they transitioned to Grade 7. This issue is consistently reflected in the annual feedback provided by the neighboring secondary schools, namely Baggao National Agricultural School, which receive learners from Taguntungan Elementary School, and Sta. Margarita National High School (formerly BNAS Annex), which caters to graduates of Sta. Margarita West Elementary School. Reports from these institutions indicate that many incoming Grade 7 learners experience difficulties in reading comprehension, fluency, and overall literacy skills, which consequently affected their academic performance across various subject areas. It is a matter of concern shared by many educators regarding the inability of graduates to read proficiently. This concern propelled the researcher to initiate an intensive intervention program to address this critical issue.

The key to cater the needs of these learners is the promotion and conduct of appropriate reading interventions and strategies to elevate the performance of learners to a higher level in oral reading and comprehending a text as well to elevate the academic performance of the pupils.

Project R.E.A.D. is aligned with the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) No. 4: Quality Education, which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. Through the implementation of reading intervention activities, the project helps learners develop essential literacy skills, improve comprehension, and strengthen their confidence in learning.

By providing accessible, engaging, and learner-centered reading experiences, Project R.E.A.D. supports the goal of improving educational outcomes and reducing learning gaps among pupils. Furthermore, the project promotes lifelong learning by cultivating a love for reading and encouraging continuous personal and academic growth among learners.

According to Hildebrand, 2019 – “Using effective reading intervention strategies is the key when working with our struggling readers. It is not only what is taught that matters; the way it is taught has a huge impact on student learning. Using reading intervention strategies that work can be the difference in helping your struggling readers learn to read.”

It was mentioned that there are five (5) main areas in reading that make up a well-rounded and solid reading foundation. These areas are “The Big 5 Reading Areas”. Developing all five (5) of these areas is crucial to learners reading success. These are Phonemic Awareness Intervention Strategies, Phonics Intervention Strategies, Fluency Intervention Strategies, Reading Comprehension Intervention Strategies, and Vocabulary Intervention Strategies.

Furthermore, it is very important to identify reading gaps in child’s learning with appropriate reading assessments and to track their progress in these crucial areas—phonemic awareness and phonics. These would tell which intervention strategies are working and when there is a need to readjust the strategies.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of Project Read, Enjoy, and Discover (READ) in Grades 4, 5, and 6 pupils of Taguntungan Elementary School and Sta. Margarita West Elementary School of Baggao North District as a basis for an enhanced reading program.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the pupils of Taguntungan Elementary School and Sta. Margarita West Elementary School of Baggao North District in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Sex
 - 1.3. Grade level
 - 1.4. Parents’ Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.5. Mothers’ Occupation
 - 1.6. Fathers’ Occupation
 - 1.7. Parents’ Gross Monthly Income

2. What is the reading level of the pupils based on the result of Phil-IRI Assessment at the Beginning of the School Year (BoSY)?
3. What is the reading level of the pupils after the intervention had been given at the End of the School Year (EoS)?
4. Is there a significant difference on the reading level of the pupils before and after the intervention?
5. Is there a significant difference on the reading level of the pupils of the two schools?
6. Is there a significant relationship on the reading level of the pupils and to their profile variables?
7. What enhanced reading program can be proposed to improve the reading level of the pupils?

Significance of the Study

This study provided a practical framework to mitigate reading problems in fostering better oral reading profile through intensified reading intervention program and deemed beneficial to the following:

Schools. The study would serve as guide to design more effective Reading Programs, Reading Interventions, and promote Reading Best Practices and Best Strategies that could address the needs, interest and problems of learners which would be necessary in promoting better academic performance by increasing and strengthening higher levels of achievement motivation to learners.

District Reading Coordinators. This study would provide invaluable insights and empirical evidence that could significantly guide and inform the decisions and actions of District Reading Coordinators in the realm of education. The research outcomes would serve as a cornerstone for shaping, refining, and implementing intensified reading intervention programs.

Administrators. This would help them conduct and implement intensive and extensive reading intervention program to schools to acquire higher level of reading achievement in their district and to promote quality education.

Teachers. The study would enable teachers to adopt effective and improved methods of reading strategies necessary to make the teaching and learning more interesting, more attractive and more enjoyable.

Parents. The study would serve as a basis to properly guide and help their children in the difficulties of reading which would likewise move them to understanding causes of their children's low performance in reading.

Learners. The study would serve as an evaluation, assessment and tool to help learners to their reading needs and to enhance their reading skills and will eventually develop them to be a better and effective reader.

Researcher. The results of this study would be utilized as a framework of reference to conduct similar studies including other pertinent variables which would lead to the improvement of reading strategies and competencies.

Future Researchers. The study would provide them a basis to conduct further research on similar studies and improve the existing reading intervention strategies or develop more strategic intervention to help the learners to acquire basic skills and help the future reading teachers.

Future Reading Teachers. The result of this study would help them in delivering smooth intervention reading strategies and equip pupils with strong reading skills for the next grade level. This could lead to a smoother transition academically, as they are more likely to grasp new concepts and handle more complex reading materials with ease. It would increase independence, for Proficient readers could work more independently, which could free up the teacher's time for more individualized instruction or for working with learners who may need extra support in other areas.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study focused on the evaluation of the reading skills and reading performance of the pupils of Taguntungan Elementary School and Sta. Margarita West Elementary School for School Year 2025–2026, with a total of 75 pupils.

To address this concern, the study implemented a reading intervention program known as Project Read, Enjoy, and Discover (R.E.A.D.), which aimed to enhance learners' reading comprehension, fluency, and overall literacy skills through engaging and structured reading activities.

Furthermore, the researcher utilized the Department of Education Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Package 2018 as the primary tool for the reading intervention and employed the grade-level reading passages provided in the kit to assess and enhance the learners' reading abilities.

Subsequently, the intervention was conducted twice a week from the first quarter to the second quarter of School Year 2025–2026, covering a six-month intervention period. Sessions were held from 1:00 PM to 2:00 PM following the designated schedule: Mondays and Tuesdays at Sta. Margarita West Elementary School, and Wednesdays and Thursdays at Taguntungan Elementary School.

Thereafter, pupils who failed the Beginning of the School Year (BoSY) Phil-IRI Group Screening Test (GST) underwent a pre-test, intervention, and post-test. The 75 struggling readers were identified during the GST and were labeled as the participants of the study. The pre-test was administered to determine their oral reading levels, namely independent, instructional, and frustration levels.

Moreover, Project R.E.A.D. (Read, Enjoy, and Discover) served as the reading intervention program conducted for six months and consisted of three phases: the Reading Phase, Enjoying Phase, and Discovering Phase. During the first month, the researcher provided lectures on how the participants could improve their reading fluency and reading comprehension skills

using different strategies such as previewing, predicting, summarizing, questioning, inferencing, visualizing, story mapping, retelling, and answering comprehension questions.

In addition, during the second and third months, the participants engaged in individual oral reading, group reading discussions, and peer reading sessions under the Reading Phase. Meanwhile, during the fourth and fifth months, the participants were exposed to more complex reading texts under the Discovering Phase, where they encountered texts related to science and history. Finally, the Enjoying Phase was conducted during the sixth and final month, during which the participants experienced game-based activities designed to make reading more engaging and enjoyable.

Most importantly, after six months of the reading intervention program, the Phil-IRI post-test for the End of the School Year (EoS_Y) was administered to determine whether the intervention had been effective for the participants from the two schools.

Definition of Terms

To provide a clear and common understanding on the content of this paper, the researcher defined the following terms operationally:

BoSY (Beginning of School Year). It is a term used in the Department of Education during reading assessments or in academic period that are administered during the first month of the school year to determine initial learners' reading proficiency level.

EoS_Y (End of School Year). This is defined as the final administration of reading assessments and/or academic achievement of learners after instruction and remediation.

Frustration level. It refers to a reading level of which a reader does not have adequate background level for a topic and/or cannot meet criteria for instructional levels of accuracy and rate.

Independent level. It refers to the highest level of which a pupil can read independently and with ease without the help or guidance of the teacher.

Instructional level. It refers to the challenging but manageable for the reader to read and with the assistance of the teacher.

Intervention. It refers to the act of interfering with the outcome or course especially of a condition or process as to prevent harm or improve functions such as educational intervention.

Oral reading level. It refers to the specific proficiency level at which a student can accurately and fluently read aloud a text. It is determined through assessments evaluating a student's ability to orally read texts, showcasing their word recognition, pronunciation, and expression.

Phil-IRI. It is an informal reading assessment under the Department of Education that is used to determine a student's independent, instructional, and frustration reading levels through oral reading assessment and it aims to establish the reading level profile of children in the public elementary school system.

Phonemic awareness. It refers to the specific ability to focus on and manipulate individual sounds (phonemes) in spoken words. Phonemes are the smallest units comprising spoken language. Phonemes combine to form syllables and words.

Project R.E.A.D. It is an acronym representing a reading intervention program which stands for "Read, Enjoy and Discover." It is a specialized program designed to offer targeted and comprehensive reading interventions specifically tailored for struggling readers who face challenges in achieving proficient reading skills.

Reading comprehension. It refers to the ability to process written text, understand its meaning, and to integrate with what the reader already knows. Reading comprehension relies on two abilities that are connected to each other: word reading and language comprehension.

Reading intervention. It refers to the intensive/ extensive or targeted instruction on reading to accelerate those who are reading below grade level

Reading programs. It refers to a consistent school-wide approach to reading instruction, an overarching framework that provides clear direction to teachers about "What to Teach and How to Teach" it so that there is clarity and consistency and success for the learners.

Reading strategies. It refers to the planned and explicit actions that help readers translate print to meaning. Strategies that improve decoding and reading comprehension skills benefit every student, but are essential for beginning readers, struggling readers, and English Language Learners.

Struggling readers. It refers to the students who exhibit difficulty in achieving age-appropriate reading skills or reading proficiency comparable to their grade level. These students may experience challenges in decoding, fluency, comprehension, or a combination thereof, impacting their overall reading performance.

School reading profile. It refers to a comprehensive and detailed analysis or report outlining various aspects of a school's reading program. It encompasses an overview of reading instruction approaches, assessment methods, intervention strategies, and student reading performance data.

METHODS AND PROCEDURES

This chapter presents the Research Design, Participants of the Study, Data Gathering Tools, Data Gathering Procedure, and Statistical Tools used in the study

Research Design

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design to assess the effectiveness of Project Read, Enjoy, and Discover (R.E.A.D.) as the basis for an enhanced reading program for School Year 2025–2026. Specifically, the researcher utilized the Two-Group Pretest-Posttest Design, wherein two groups of pupil-participants underwent a pre-test and post-test before and after the implementation of the reading intervention. The reading scores obtained from the pre-test and post-test were compared to determine whether the intervention improved the participants' reading performance.

Moreover, the study also employed a correlational approach to examine the relationship between the participants' profile variables and their reading skills. This approach aimed to determine the strength and direction of the relationship among the variables involved in the study.

Through the integration of quasi-experimental and correlational methods, the study provided a comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of the Project R.E.A.D. intervention and its relationship to the participants' reading abilities.

Participants of the Study

The study focused on the reading skills and reading performance of the participants. The researcher studied two small schools in Baggao North District, namely Taguntungan Elementary School and Sta. Margarita West Elementary School, which had reported similar concerns regarding low reading performance based on feedback from neighboring secondary schools.

The intervention program was conducted among the intermediate grades of the two mentioned schools, specifically Grades 4, 5, and 6 pupils, with a total of 75 participants.

Total enumeration was used by the researcher, wherein all participants identified as having low reading levels during the Group Screening Test underwent the intervention program. This was done for the purpose of developing the participants' reading skills and improving their reading profile. The table below presents the distribution of the respondents:

Table 1

Distribution of Pupil-Participants

Participants	Grade Level	Number of Participants	Total Population (N)
Taguntungan Elementary School	Grade 4	9	38
	Grade 5	14	
	Grade 6	15	
Sta. Margarita West Elementary School	Grade 4	11	37
	Grade 5	15	
	Grade 6	11	
Total		75	75

Data Gathering Tool

With the goal of improving the reading skills of struggling pupils in the two participating schools, namely Taguntungan Elementary School and Sta. Margarita West Elementary School, the intervention program called Project R.E.A.D. (“Read, Enjoy, and Discover”) was implemented to address reading difficulties among struggling readers.

The tool used in this study was the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). It is the Department of Education’s (DepEd) assessment tool used in public elementary and secondary schools to measure students’ reading speed, oral reading fluency, and comprehension in both English and Filipino. It helped teachers identify pupils’ reading levels—Independent, Instructional, or Frustration—to design targeted reading interventions.

Furthermore, the participants in this study underwent a series of reading activities conducted before the official class hours in the afternoon. This promoted good reading habits among pupils through an intensive and continuous process aimed at achieving the primary goal of making pupils competent readers.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before the conduct of the study, the researcher secured a certification from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) to formally initiate the research process. A letter was also furnished to the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS)/District In-Charge of Baggao North District to request approval for the conduct of the study. In addition, the researcher sought permission through letters addressed to the School Principals of the two participating schools, Taguntungan Elementary School and Sta. Margarita West Elementary School. Parental consent

was likewise secured from the parents or guardians of the participants to allow their participation in the study.

Furthermore, the pre-test results obtained from the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) assessment served as the baseline data for the intervention program. After the administration of the pre-test, the reading levels of the participants were determined to proceed with the reading intervention.

During the intervention, the participants attended the “one o’clock reading intervention habit” to foster a love for reading and develop their reading skills. Throughout the duration of the intervention program, the researcher applied a series of strategies such as Individual Silent Reading, Individual Oral Reading, Guided Reading, and Independent Reading, along with comprehension activities from the Phil-IRI package.

Additionally, the intervention was conducted twice a week from the first quarter to the second quarter of School Year 2025–2026, covering a six-month intervention period. Sessions were held from 1:00 PM to 2:00 PM following the designated schedule: Mondays and Tuesdays at Sta. Margarita West Elementary School, and Wednesdays and Thursdays at Taguntungan Elementary School.

After the implementation of the interventions, the researcher administered the post-reading assessment (post-test) to determine whether there was an improvement in the reading skills of the pupils. The results of the pre-test and post-test were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The data gathered were tabulated, evaluated, and analyzed using percentage to identify the reading levels of the pupils and to determine the effectiveness of the intervention. This was done to comprehensively determine whether there was a relative improvement in the participants’ oral reading and comprehension skills and whether the intervention had a significant effect after implementation.

Statistical Tools

The gathered data in this study were carefully analyzed using the following statistical tools to ensure the accuracy, reliability, and validity of the findings:

Mean and standard deviation were utilized to determine the oral reading levels of the pupils during the pretest and posttest. The mean was used to identify the average performance of the learners in terms of their reading abilities, while the standard deviation measured the degree of variation or dispersion of the scores. These statistical tools provided a clearer understanding of the pupils’ overall reading performance before and after the implementation of Project R.E.A.D.

Additionally, to determine whether there was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the participants, the Paired Sample T-test was employed. This statistical tool was appropriate because it compared two related sets of scores obtained from the same group of pupils before and after the intervention. Through this analysis, the researcher was able to assess whether the reading intervention program resulted in a significant improvement in the learners’ reading performance.

Moreover, the Independent T-test was used to determine whether a significant difference existed between the two groups of participants. This test enabled the researcher to compare the reading performance of pupils from the two participating schools and identify whether variations in their results were statistically significant. The use of this statistical method provided a basis for comparing the effectiveness of the intervention across different groups of learners.

Furthermore, Pearson r and the Chi-square test were utilized to determine the relationship between the pupils' reading skills and their profile variables. Pearson r was used to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between continuous variables, while the Chi-square test examined the association between categorical variables. These statistical tools helped the researcher identify whether factors related to the pupils' profiles had significant relationships with their reading performance and development.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the Summary of Findings, Conclusion, and Recommendations that were obtained after undertaking careful analysis and interpretation of the gathered data.

Summary of Findings

In light of the results and discussion, the following are the key findings:

1. Profile of the Pupils

- Almost all pupils were in their appropriate age, majority were male, and most were in grade 5. Most of the pupils' mothers are high school graduates, while their fathers had completed elementary education. In addition, majority of their mothers' occupation was housekeeping, while their fathers' was farming, and majority came from poor families.

2. Reading level of the pupils based on the result of Phil-IRI Assessment in the Beginning of School Year (BoSY).

- Majority of the participants from both schools were classified under the frustration reading level before the implementation of the intervention, indicating low oral reading proficiency among the pupils.

3. Oral reading level of the pupils after the intervention had been given at the End of School Year (EoSY).

- Majority of the participants remained under the frustration level after the intervention; however, there was an increase in the number of participants who progressed to the instructional and independent reading levels, especially in Taguntungan Elementary School.

4. Comparison on the reading level of the pupils before and after the intervention.

- There was a statistically significant difference between the pre-test and post-test reading levels of the learners. The intervention produced a moderate effect on the pupil-

participants' reading performance, indicating that the intervention was effective in improving reading skills.

5. Comparison of the reading level of the pupils of the two schools.

- There was a statistically significant difference between the reading levels of pupils from the two schools, showing that Taguntungan Elementary School participants performed better than Sta. Margarita Elementary School.

6. Correlation on the reading level of the pupils when grouped according to their profile variables

- Among the profile variables, only the pupil-participants' age and grade level showed a significant relationship with their reading level.

7. (Output) Proposed enhanced reading program to improve the reading level of the pupils

- With the result and findings, the researcher proposed Project Read, Enjoy and Discover (R.E.A.D) with continuous effort in improving pupils' reading skills, comprehension, vocabulary development, and critical thinking skills through engaging and meaningful reading activities. This project aims to cultivate pupils' interest in reading, enhance their academic performance, and promote lifelong learning through collaborative support from teachers, parents, and the school community.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that the implementation of Project R.E.A.D. was effective in improving the reading performance of the pupils. The significant improvement observed between the pre-test and post-test results confirmed that the intervention contributed to the development of pupils' oral reading skills, particularly in fluency, pronunciation, word recognition, and comprehension. Although many participants remained at the frustration level, several participants progressed to the instructional and independent levels after the intervention.

Furthermore, the comparison between the two schools revealed that pupils from Taguntungan Elementary School performed significantly better than those from Sta. Margarita West Elementary School after the intervention, suggesting differences in the implementation and effectiveness of the reading intervention program.

Finally, the correlation analysis revealed that age and grade level were significantly associated with oral reading performance. This implies that developmental maturity and increased exposure to reading instruction contributed to the improvement of pupils' reading abilities. Therefore, continuous and structured reading interventions are essential in enhancing pupils' reading skills and reducing the number of frustrated readers.

Recommendations

The following were humbly recommended by the researcher based on the findings and conclusion drawn:

1. Schools may integrate structured and sustained reading intervention programs like Project R.E.A.D, especially in the early grade levels to strengthen foundational literacy skills and address the diverse learning needs of pupils. By embedding engaging and developmentally appropriate reading activities into classroom instruction, learners may develop better comprehension, vocabulary, fluency, and critical thinking skills. Furthermore, the integration of reading intervention programs can help create a more learner-centered curriculum that promotes active participation, academic achievement, and lifelong learning habits among pupils.
2. District Reading Coordinators may formulate intensive reading programs like Project R.E.A.D that may help support the implementation of school-based reading interventions and allocate resources for reading materials, teacher training, and regular reading assessments.
3. School Administrators should strengthen the implementation and monitoring of reading programs to effectively implement the intervention across grade levels.
4. Teachers may adopt and continuously apply reading intervention strategies similar to Project R.E.A.D to ensure improvement on the oral reading performance of the learners.
5. Parents are encouraged to conduct regular reading practice at home and provide a supportive environment that motivates their child to read.
6. Learners should participate in reading activities and practice reading regularly to further improve their reading fluency and comprehension.
7. Researcher should develop more innovative and sustainable literacy programs like Project R.E.A.D that address the diverse learning needs of learners in different educational contexts. The findings may likewise encourage the researcher to conduct further investigations on factors affecting reading performance, parental involvement, learner motivation, and the integration of technology in reading instruction to support quality education and lifelong learning.
8. Future Researchers may conduct similar study or other reading interventions in different contexts, and explore additional factors that may influence learners' reading development. They may also explore the effectiveness of various reading intervention programs, instructional approaches, and learner-centered activities in enhancing pupils' reading comprehension, fluency, vocabulary, and critical thinking skills.
9. Future Reading Teachers may use and adopt Project R.E.A.D as their intervention program to help them in equipping their pupils with strong reading skills, improved comprehension, and greater confidence in reading. Through the implementation of varied and engaging reading activities, teachers can provide meaningful learning experiences that address the diverse needs of learners. Moreover, the Project R.E.A.D may serve as a guide in developing innovative strategies and sustainable reading practices that will encourage pupils to become active, independent, and lifelong readers.

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